

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FINANCIAL TOOLS FOR ASSESSING MARKETING ACTIVITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7738703>

Abstract

The elements for achieving the success of the company are the development of a strategy and competent goalsetting, risk assessment, allocation of resources, and direct implementation of activities. Customer perspectives, primarily related to marketing, are one of the most important aspects of shaping the sustainable success of an organization. Their planning, control, and evaluation become the most significant factors for the stable operation of the enterprise. Thus, the use of marketing metrics plays a huge role in ensuring the success of an organization.

The study of the theoretical basis for evaluating marketing decisions, as well as the analysis of Western studies, made it possible to form a comprehensive system of financial evaluation of various aspects of the company's marketing activities, considering both digital and traditional marketing channels, and different levels of management in the company. In practice, this approach allows you to get more accurate data for planning marketing activities, as well as justifying marketing decisions. According to the results of an empirical study of Georgian companies, this is a serious problem for modern Georgian businesses.

Keywords: marketing efficiency, marketing effectiveness, marketing metrics, controlling.

Introduction. The issues of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing decisions have been discussed for a long time, and in digitalization and changes in the speed of market development, this issue becomes even more relevant.

The goal of the company's management is always to maximize financial results, and all company analytics are implemented, mainly using financial indicators. Financial control provides the management of the company with the management reporting data necessary to maintain effective leadership and achieve business success. The results of marketing activities are extremely important.

Marketing matters do not always have a clear financial description. While a company's marketing department is always the cost center and therefore requires a clear justification for the investment, the result of a company's investment in marketing is shared between sales departments (e.g. regional sales, retail sales, etc.) and marketing departments. Another big challenge is the need to invest in and evaluate the effectiveness of public relations activities.

We should remember we can make marketing decisions at the strategic, tactical, and operational levels, which also require different approaches to evaluating results and applying different metrics that can be applied.

Financial Controlling and Marketing Activities of the Company. To implement the control of the company's activities, including marketing activities, it is

necessary to have operational, reliable, and complete information, which is achieved through the creation of a controlling system at the enterprise [8]. Receipt, regular analysis, and development of measures based on them allow the company to improve business processes, achieve its goals, and, as a result, ensure the economic security and success of the company.

Thus, the development of controlling is primarily due to the need of the business, since the controlling of the company's business processes ensures the relationship between the company's strategy and operational actions and allows you to control the situation, make appropriate decisions, and, thanks to this, achieve a state of economic security.

An analysis of international experience made it possible to identify two areas of controlling concepts: those focused on achieving results and those focused on the implementation of universal goals [7] (Table 1).

Under the presented periodization of the development of control, already in the 60s, the issues of cost accounting and ensuring the effectiveness of sales, and the marketing activities of the company come relevant. Because in the early 2000s, the focus of controlling issues was increasing the value of the business, and marketing activity is the most important component in the value formation of such an intangible asset (intangible assets) as a company brand.

Stages of Financial Controlling [5]

N	Period	Main Ideas
Stage I	Before 1950	Implementation of the technical function for the formation of the cost of production and the use of budgeting methods
Stage II	1950–1960	formation of a system of operational information for the management of the company by responsibility centers
Stage III	1960-1985	cost management and business process analysis to minimize corporate and social losses (quality control)
Stage IV	1985-1995	cost control and implementation of business processes
Stage V	1995-2005	(functional cost analysis by business processes)
Stage VI	After 2005	the strategic analysis focused on increasing business value

Without effective marketing, a company cannot count on sustainable success in the market (stage IV), thus, since the middle of the last century, marketing activities have been the focus of controlling. And since the end of the twentieth century (stages V and VI), the focus of controlling has been on issues of strategic analysis and business development related to increasing.

The value of intangible assets and the business and the formation of a stable, successful work of the company in the future at the expense of the brand.

Approaches to Evaluating the Effectiveness of the Company's Marketing Activities. The basis for achieving the sustainable success of an organization, according to the state standard, is the efficient use of resources, taking into account the needs of stakeholders, and making decisions based on facts. Due to the constant changes in the environment, the management of the organization must ensure the conditions for the stable existence of the company through planning and control, monitoring activities and assessing risks, building relationships, and assessing the satisfaction of all stakeholders. The choice of key performance indicators by the organization should ensure the improvement of the efficiency and effectiveness of processes and take into account the expectations of customers, the importance of individual types of products, profitability and financial performance, and legal requirements.

O. K. Oyner develops ideas about the dual nature of the concept of "efficiency", which corresponds to the ideas of other authors [12, 13]. At the same time, efficiency characterizes the economic assessment of the activity (cost) and is calculated as the ratio of the result to the cost of the event, and the effectiveness shows the ability to achieve the goals and is largely based on qualitative assessments. In addition, Euner identifies "internal" and "external" efficiency, showing the degree of achievement of short-term and strategic goals, respectively.

Indicators of efficiency and effectiveness can be classified as general (integral). In addition, indicators are often considered that are of a private (local) nature, for which it is customary to use the concept marketing metrics (in foreign sources, the term marketing performance metrics (MPM) is used), which is considered a system of indicators that help form certain characteristics [American Marketing Association et al., 2011].

The private nature of marketing metrics can be traced in the work of Donald A. Marshall with co-authors, who write about the need for their strict compliance with the goals of marketing and business, that is,

a lower, subordinate character. The authors consider the concept of marketing metrics and, based on the analysis of twelve definitions, identify the characteristics of the term "marketing metrics", such as its quantitative nature and measurability, a certain dimension, purpose (assessment of the results of marketing activities) and a clear correspondence to business goals. [15] The authors see the regular nature of measurements as an important aspect in the use of marketing metrics (at least 1-2 times a year). And their application should provide the company with a quantitative assessment of marketing activities and focus on the most priority areas of marketing activities.

There are a fairly large number of classifications of marketing metrics. Most of them correspond to the classifications of indicators into absolute and relative, strategic and operational, evaluating short-term and long-term results, and others [15, 10].

In addition, many authors identify financial and non-financial metrics [Malcolm, 2004; Kotler, Keller, 2007] or talk about financial indicators or metrics for evaluating marketing activities [Farris et al., 2010, Sampaio et al., 2011, Ambler, 2003, Kokkinaki, Ambler, 1999, Pilling, Rigdon, Brightman, 2012, Mintz, Currim, 2013].

In addition to marketing metrics, in the literature, one can often find a review of various methods for evaluating the effectiveness of marketing decisions [16]. A large number of methods are distinguished, including sociological and scoring methods, but most often it is customary to talk about quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative methods involve the use of multidimensional, simulation, statistical, and other methods. Qualitative methods, in addition to qualitative research, include marketing controlling and audit, and analysis of the components of marketing activities.

Methods of Research

The article uses methods of analysis and synthesis, applies analogy and comparison, and summarizes information from various sources and approaches to the definition of marketing metrics.

An empirical study of thirty Georgian enterprises is being carried out, because of which we identify the main metrics of the financial perspective for evaluating the effectiveness of activities. The study involved sending questionnaires, comprising 20 questions, according to a previously developed list of enterprises. The return of questionnaires was 10%.

We analyzed various studies in terms of the development of marketing metrics, which are summarized and compared with the results of the empirical study.

Based on the analysis of various studies, identified the main financial metrics for evaluating the effectiveness of activities. It carried the analysis out for the company, individual departments, and online and offline environments.

Based on the study of the goals and objectives of financial controlling, a system of financial metrics is being developed to evaluate the effectiveness of activities, which will be understandable to financial management and will contribute to the sustainable success of the company.

Research Results

The main indicator characterizing the financial results of marketing activities is the return on marketing investment (ROMI or MROI) [17]. The complexity of calculating the indicator lies in the difficulty of highlighting the increase in profit (value) because of marketing activities.

It implemented an attempt to link financial and marketing aspects with other parameters for the success of the company in the balanced scorecard (BSC). The authors of the balanced scorecard R. Kaplan and D. Norton [4] identify four aspects that ensure the success of the company's strategic management:

- Financial, which characterizes the shareholders' vision of financial indicators;
- Client, reflecting the vision of customers, expressed in qualitative indicators characterizing customer satisfaction;
- Aspect of internal processes that characterize the performance indicators of the internal processes of the organization;
- Aspect of learning and growth that describes the human and intellectual capital of a company.

The ideas of Kaplan R., and Norton D., were applied by G. Guchetl directly for marketing activities [3]. In G. Guchetl's approach, the prospect of "customer relations" instead of the "price" element also identified four perspectives, corresponding to the three elements of the marketing mix and supplemented.

M. Jeffrey [2] suggested using 15 key indicators that allow you to evaluate the effectiveness, which includes the following financial indicators: profit, net present value, internal rate of return, payback, cost per click, return on investment in advertising, and customer lifetime value (CLV). It is necessary to take revenge that Farris, P., Bandle, N., Pfaijer, P. [6] singles out the last indicator, naming the value of the client during the period of his loyalty to the firm, among the three key indicators besides MROI and the customer retention rate (CRR).

The KPI Institute reviewed the top 25 marketing performance indicators for 2016 and highlighted the following financial metrics: customer acquisition cost (annual cost to gain new customers relative to the number of new customers gained), customer profitability, customer lifetime value, cost of customer retention, marketing spend per customer, marketing ROI. In addition, two indicators partially characterize the financial component of the issue: relative price (the price of

a product in relation to the average price of goods of similar purpose and quality) and the price elasticity of demand (change in the number of buyers of a product depending on the price of the product).

According to a study by T. Ambler [1], it is the financial metrics for evaluating the effectiveness activities that are most often used, the most important of which are profit and profitability, sales volume, and gross profit (over 80% of the analyzed companies are used). The relative price of a product, marketing costs, income and profit from new products, price elasticity of demand, and the size of discounts are also analyzed less frequently.

Henry Assel [11, p.111] identifies identified the following financial metrics for evaluating marketing activities: metrics for assessing financial aspects (sales and profits), and pricing metrics (changes in prices for the company's products). Using the example of the public catering sector, Assel singles out financial, market, and brand metrics, while financial ones include sales volume, marketing costs, and profit. In addition, it identified metrics for evaluating the effectiveness of activities on the Internet, which are divided into basic, and special, related to content, SEO optimization, PR, and branding. Financial metrics mainly fall into the group of basic ones. These are the cost of a click, the cost of a target action, and the cost of a sale.

Indeed, the approach to evaluating the effectiveness of activities on the Internet has significant differences from the traditional one. First, this is because of the ease of obtaining the data and the ability to assess the impact of each factor that generates revenue and the visibility of the data. However, the correct interpretation of data requires certain knowledge and an established analytics system in the company. According to American research conducted by the Safefrog Marketing Group marketing agency in 2017 [16], American companies use a whole range of indicators that characterize activities both online and offline. Some of the most commonly used metrics include:

- 1) Behavioral: leads, traffic, site traffic in relation to the number of leads;
- 2) Quality of service: response time of sales staff, number of customers from the website, conversion from gained customers to actual completed transactions, email marketing performance (delivery rate, unsubscribe rate, availability, etc.), number of customers compared to the number of visitors website, conversion from attracted clients to offered offers, conversion from commercial offers to completed transactions;
- 3) Cost sales volume and its division by departments and employees, by the lifetime value of the client, and by the cost of attracting a client.

At the same time, the analyzed American B2B companies opt for Internet marketing tools and use the following metrics to evaluate communications in the digital environment:

- ROMI, CTR (Click-thru-rate) for direct marketing evaluation,
- CPC (cost-per-click) to estimate the cost of one contact,
- COCA (Cost of Customer Acquisition), CPL(Cost Per Lea) or the cost of one interested client

(lead),

- CTB (Click-To-Buy ratio) or the ratio of the number of buyers to the total number of visitors to the resource,
- CTI (click-to-interest) is calculated as the ratio of the number of interested users to the total number of visits to the site,

VTR (ratio of views to the total number of impressions). We should note that all the studied companies evaluate the effectiveness using at least five of the most appropriate metrics selected under the characteristics of the enterprise.

The authors conducted a similar study of Georgian companies to analyze the most popular metrics for evaluating marketing activities in the online and offline environment, because of which it was revealed that CTR - 70%, ROMI - 50%, and CPC - 40% are used among the main indicators, other metrics are small popular or not used at all. This suggests that, despite the availability of the same opportunities for evaluating the effectiveness decisions, Georgian companies use evaluation metrics extremely poorly, which leads to the poor justification of marketing activities, a misunderstanding of their effectiveness, and connection with business goals.

We compared the results of a study of American companies conducted by the Safefrog Marketing Group

[16] and the results of a study of Georgian enterprises conducted by us. It turned out that the validity of the action and the assessment of the effectiveness of activities in Georgian companies are superficial. In addition, they do not allow to ensure the stability of the work and economic security of the company in the future. In contrast, American companies use many marketing metrics and exercise fairly strict control of marketing activities, which provides them with more stable work and allows them to achieve success in the market.

Companies receive a large amount of information thanks to the information systems and Internet resources used. However, because of the presence of many indicators of marketing activities, it is rather difficult for companies to determine the minimum that could provide specialists and managers of the company's marketing department with data on evaluating marketing decisions and provide the information base for financial management and company management to ensure stability and success Business.

According to the results of the study, most companies lack precisely the financial assessment of the results of marketing activities, which is also necessary for the formation of an integrated system for controlling marketing activities and financial reporting to provide the company's management with reliable information for making management decisions (Table 2).

Table 2.

Hierarchy of financial metrics for evaluating marketing activities

Integral indicators	Marketing Performance	Company Management Level	Profit Revenue
		Level of Financial Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marketing costs - MROI - HMA cost - ROS
Marketing Metrics	Marketing Effectiveness	Company marketing Management Level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marketing costs - Cost structure - MROI by department - COCA - CRC¹ - LTV - MCC² - PPC³
	External Efficiency	The level of line managers in the field of marketing of the company	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost structure of the department (by functions and employees) - MROI by events - COCA department - CRC department - PPC
	Internal Efficiency	Employee Level (online environment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CPC - PPC - CPL - COCA - CRC - Internet marketing costs
		Employee Level (offline environment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRP⁴ - PPC - CPT⁵ - COCA - AVE⁶ - Costs for individual events - CRC

¹ Customer retention cost

² Marketing cost per client

³ Profits per customer

⁴ Cost per Rating Point

⁵ Cost per thousand contacts

⁶ Advertising Value Equivalent

The table proposes a hierarchy of financial metrics for evaluating the marketing activities of a company, which considers traditional and Internet marketing, in which only cost indicators are grouped that meet the needs of modern companies in the financial evaluation of marketing activities at various levels of responsibility. The regularity of calculation and tracking in the system's dynamics of indicators proposed based on the analysis of Georgian and foreign experience and the study of various publications will allow companies to receive operational statistics, and evaluate and develop new marketing activities, having a clearer justification for this.

Conclusion. Modern business cannot exist without marketing activities and requires an appropriate assessment of marketing activities. A huge number of existing indicators lead to the fact that companies use the most obvious minimum, without understanding the value and capabilities of others. This is what we found in the process of empirical research, which was confirmed by the results of other studies.

When using marketing performance indicators, the most significant issues are the allocation of resources at the stage of developing marketing programs, as well as the final control showing the degree to which the company's goals have been achieved. In addition, it is important to assess the risks of marketing activities, which comprise the loss incurred or lost income in the company's implementation of marketing strategy. Here, the main risk factors include an incorrect assessment of the company's external environment factors (research part), incorrect definition of business goals in the current conditions and directions of action (goal setting and strategy development), the wrong choice of tools and evaluation criteria (marketing decisions - the implementation of activities). As a result, there is a risk of not getting the planned result, which is an indicator of the inefficiency of marketing activities and the work of the company.

Thus, financial control in relation to marketing activities should be implemented in three main perspectives:

- 1) Control of the use of resources for the implementation of marketing activities,
- 2) Monitoring the results of marketing activities in terms understandable to financial management,
- 3) Risk assessment of marketing activities.

Using the system of financial indicators proposed by the authors based on the study of the experience of mainly foreign companies, Western studies, and domestic and international publications will contribute to a clearer development and control of marketing deci-

sions at various levels of marketing management. In addition, it will help to integrate the results of marketing activities into the overall controlling system and improve the efficiency of decisions made at various levels of management, as well as achieve more stable results and sustainable success of the organization.

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